

Review Article

Advances in Pyrazole Ring Formation and Their Methodologies: Review

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this review was to discuss the pyrazole synthesis method. The significance of significant groups of heterocyclic compounds that generate pyrazoles has only increased due to their broad range of biological activity-based research areas. The biological functions of pyrazole are diverse. These compounds are employed in pharmacological research and the creation of agricultural goods. The aim of this review is to offer a comprehensive overview of the published research related to the synthesis of pyrazole derivatives, encompassing a discussion of diverse methods for accessing the pyrazole moiety, The technique created for synthesis of pyrazole are therefore becoming increasingly significant.

INTRODUCTION

Pyrazole, a five-membered heterocycle containing two nitrogen atoms¹, More over half of all known chemical compounds are heterocycles, which are important types of molecules. several drugs, the majority of supplements, several natural products, and biomolecules such as hormones, antibiotics, alkaloids, vitamins, and so forth include them.²In fact, pyrazoles are a broad family of heterocycles that may be investigated for the creation of novel pharmaceutical compounds.³The simplest member of pyrazole family is pyrazole itself, a compound with molecular formulae C₃H₄N₂⁴. 1,2,4-triazoles

have been well documented⁵.Heterocyclic structural elements are included in the great majority of synthetic medications that are sold commercially². they are found in a large number of drugs and naturally occurring molecules with antifungal⁶, antiparasitic, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antihypertensive, analgesic⁷, antiviral, and antidiabetic activity just a few of the many heterocyclic compounds that have been shown to have broad range of biological properties.⁸ Pyrazoles are highly versatile and find applications in various industries including chemicals, pharmaceuticals, medications, and agriculture⁹, polymer

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chemistry.¹⁰ One kind of heterocyclic chemical is pyrazole. First, pyrazole was produced in Figure 1 by decarboxylating pyrazol-3,4,5-tricarboxylic acid.¹¹

Pyrazole was thought to be non-existent from nature until recently. However, a Japanese plant belonging to the Tropical Asiatic "Piperaceae" family identified the first naturally occurring pyrazole derivative. We extracted pyrazolic amino acids from watermelon seeds (*Citrullus vulgaris*).

¹¹ Ludwig Knorr originally used the term "pyrazole" in 1883¹². Due to their widespread presence in natural products, nitrogen-containing heterocycles are among the most active substances. Numerous applications in biology, chemistry, and other disciplines are also demonstrated by them. Furthermore, heterocycles containing nitrogen are important in coordination chemistry². The five-membered heterocycle 1H-pyrazole, on the other hand, belongs to a family of substances that have drawn a lot of interest because of its synthesis and efficient significance for biology¹³. Many physiologically significant natural compounds and alkaloids, including serotonin, vitamin B1, morphine, atropine, coniine, nicotine, caffeine, and different NSAIDs, include subunits of these cores¹⁴. In our earlier study, 3,4-diaryl-1H-pyrazoles derivatives were produced and their antioxidant properties were evaluated. These compounds showed antibodies to heat-shock protein 70 and anticancer¹⁵. Hydrazine derivatives of 1,3-diketones. The synthesis of pyrazole derivatives using the pyrazole as the central core is the focus of another method. Our goal is to examine the processes involved in the

synthesis of several additional substituted and condensed pyrazoles, namely the potential of 5-chloro- and 5-azido-1,3-diphenyl-1H pyrazole-4-carbaldehydes¹⁶. The carbostyryl (2-quinolone) ring system is a significant family of chemicals due to its antibacterial properties as well as its theoretical relevance¹⁷. Produce a unique 5-substituted phenyl pyrazole with a heterocyclic ring to produce some intriguing new anti-inflammatory drugs¹⁸. 3,5-Diaryl Pyrazole is chemically synthesized from α , β unsaturated ketones using a carbonyl chromophore on the N-1 position. Thus, the purpose of this research is to create 3,5-diaryl derivation of pyrazole from the precursor chalcone¹⁹. Recent years, our group have reported a number of novel pyrazole derivatives. Many FDA-approved and commercially accessible medications, both patented and non-patented, have been made with pyrazole derivatives in recent years. The widespread use of these groups in the synthesis of new bioactive chemicals is highlighted by this trend. This evaluation explains pyrazole pharmacophore synthesis in brief, making it a useful reference manual for researchers working on this area. Chemical synthesis categories are used to roughly categorize the perspective²⁰. Numerous pyrazole compounds, both natural and synthetic, have a broad range of pharmacological potentials and druggable qualities²¹. In this work, we would like to present some pyrazole derivatives that meet these structural specifications²².

Methods:

2.1 Synthesis of 3-phenyl-4-heteroaryl-1H-pyrazoles and 3,4-diphenyl-1H-pyrazoles : Zun-Ting Zhang et.al aim to performed Hydrazine hydrate (2 mmol) and compound 3-Heteroarylchromones or 3-Phenylchromones (1 mmol) were refluxed in ethanol (15 mL) for approximately two hours. TLC tracked every

reaction until the 3-heteroarylchromones were completely consumed. The combination was then put into 100 millilitres of ice water and treated with 10% HCl to bring the pH down to 6-7. Using column chromatography on silica gel

(dichloromethane), the white precipitate was filtered and purified, yielding products 4 in 75%-94% yields and 5 in 91%-96% yields. The novel compounds were 4a-4g¹⁵.

R₁=H,4-ome,4-i-opr,4-OH; R₂=H, me, R₃=H,4-ome,4-OH,4-F, CF₃; Y=O, S, N-Me

Scheme 1. General Synthetic Route for Compound 4 and 5

2.2 Synthesis of N-[(5-Azido-1,3-diphenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-yl)-methylene]-N-arylamines (4a-c): Mahmoud F. Farhata et.al discussed of After dissolving 5-azido-1,3-di phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde (3) (0.5 g, 0.002 mol) in 25 ml of ethanol, 0.2 ml of glacial acetic acid and 0.002

mol of amine were added. Overnight, the reaction mixture was left to stand at room temperature.

Filtration was used to separate the yellow crystalline precipitate (4a-c), which was then cleaned with cold ethanol¹⁶.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 5-azidopyrazole-4-methylenearylamines (4a-c).

2.3 Synthesis of N-[(5-Substituted-1,3-diphenyl-1H-pyrazole-4 yl) methylene] hydrazides (5a-e): Five-azido-1,3-diphen-yl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde (3) or five-chloro-1,3-diaryl 1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde (2) (1.30 g, 0.005 mol) was dissolved in 15 ml of ethanol, followed by the addition of 0.2 ml of glacial acetic acid and 0.005 mol of acid hydrazide. The reaction mixture was

then allowed to remain at room temperature for two hours. Filtration was used to separate the yellow crystalline precipitate (5a-e), which was then cleaned with ethanol. While the azido compounds (5d,e) were utilized without additional purification, the chloropyrazole hydrazides (5a-c) were crystallized from ethanol.¹⁶

a: R = Ph, X = Cl; b: R = 4-Pyridyl, X = Cl c: R = CH₂CN, X = Cl; d: R = Ph, X = N₃ e: R = 4-Pyridyl, X = N₃
Scheme 3. Synthesis of *N*-[(5-substituted-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-4-yl)-methylene] hydrazides (5a-e).

2.4 Synthesis of 5-Arylamino-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4 carbonitriles (8a-c): Five azido-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-ylmethylene)-*N*-arylamine (4a-c) (0.0017 mol) was dissolved in fifteen milliliters of ethyl acetate and refluxed for

four hours. After concentration, the solution was chilled. Filtration was used to collect the yellow solid, which was then allowed to dry in the air before crystallizing from pet-ether (bp. 60-80)/ethyl acetate 3:1.¹⁶

Scheme 4. Formation of 5-arylamino-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-carbonitriles (8a-c)

2.5 Synthesis of *N*-(4-Cyano-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5-yl) hydrazide derivatives (13a,b): A solution of 5-azido 1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)methylenehydrazides (5d,e) (0.0015 mol) in toluene (15 ml) was refluxed for 2h. The solution was concentrated and cooled and the yellow solid separated was collected by filtration, dried in air and crystallized from pet-ether (bp. 60-80)/ ethyl acetate 3:1.¹⁶

were refluxed in 50 milliliters of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) with a little amount of anhydrous ZnCl₂. After cooling and pouring the reaction mixture over crushed ice, the resulting yellow solid was filtered out, cleaned with water, and crystallized from ethanol.¹⁶

2.6 Synthesis of *N*-[2-(5-Chloro-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-4-oxo-thiazolidin-3-yl]amides (14a,b): For six hours, *N*-[(5 chloro-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-4-yl)methylene]hydrazide (5a,b) (0.015 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol)

2.7 Synthesis of 3-Acetyl-2-(5-chloro-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-aryl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (15a, b): Excess acetic anhydride (10 ml) and *N*-[(5 chloro-1,3-diphenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-4-yl) methyl ene] hydrazide (5a, b) (0.00145 mol) was refluxed for two hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured onto ice that had been crushed. After filtering, water washing, air drying, and crystallization from ethanol, the yellow precipitate was produced.¹⁶

Scheme 7. Some reactions of (5-substituted-1,3-diphenyl-1H-pyrazol-yl) methylene hydrazides (5a, b,d, e).

2.8 Synthesis of 4-(3-(het)aryl-1-phenyl-1H pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-7,7-disubstituted 3,4,7,8-tetrahydroquinoline-2,5(1H,6H)-Dione:

Nilesh J. Thumar • Manish P. Patel et.al synthesis In acetonitrile (20 ml) with three drops of piperidine, a combination of 1H-3-aryl-1-phenylpyrazole-4-carbaldehyde 1a–h (30 mmol), Meldrum's acid 2 (30 mmol), and suitable b-enaminone 3a–b (30 mmol) was gradually heated and refluxed for six hours while being

stirred. Following the conclusion of the reaction, which was observed by TLC (ethyl acetate: toluene = 3:7), the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. The separated solid was then filtered and cleaned using a 1:1 combination of methanol and chloroform to yield the pure compounds 4a–p. Below are the compounds 4a p's physical, analytical, and spectroscopic characterisation results.¹⁷

Scheme 8 Synthetic pathway for the synthesis of carbostyryl derivatives of 1H-pyrazole 4a–p

2.9 Synthesis of substituted Ethyl 5-phenyl 1H-pyrazole-3-carboxylate: Gupta Sujeet Kumara et.al gives procedure A 15 mmol suspension of intermediate compound substituted ethyl 2,4-dioxo 4-phenyl-butanoates (1a-j) in glacial acetic acid (70 %, 10 ml) was mixed with a solution of

hydrazine hydrate (99%, 15 mmol). The mixture was refluxed at 80–90°C for 6–8 hours. TLC kept track of the reaction's development. To get the appropriate pyrazole derivatives (2a-j), the product was filtered, cleaned with ethanol, dried, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate.¹⁸

Scheme 9. Synthetic protocol of compounds (2a-j).

2.10 Synthesis of 1-acetyl-3,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrazole from Chalcone: Noor Hidayah Pungotlet.al synthesis After adding 3,5-Diphenyl 2-pyrazoline 4 to a flask containing 1.564 mmol of anhydrous AlCl₃, 100 mL of acetyl chloride was added. For three hours, the reaction mixture was refluxed in a sealed tube at 65°C. Using the

fractional crystallization technique, dichloromethane was used to purify the reaction after it had been agitated until all of the solids had dissolved. Then, under vacuum pressure, petroleum ether was added and filtered. After being oven-dried at 40°C, the crude product yielded a brownish solid in 0.4562 g (55%).¹⁹

Scheme 10. Overall synthetic route to compound 5

Scheme 13. Synthesis of substituted pyrazoles from 1,3-diketones and hydrazine derivative

CONCLUSION:

In summary, various pyrazole have been synthesized in this review. The substituted pyrazoles are used in different sector. As result the techniques created for this chemical production are becoming increasingly significant. Lastly, several instances of pyrazole synthesis were given. The majority of research projects follow this set of guidelines. summary, while significant progress has been made in improving both the yield and efficacy of pyrazole products, ongoing research into more efficient, selective, and sustainable synthetic methods will be key to unlocking the full potential of pyrazoles in diverse applications.

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